

D3.4 – Report of final public release of high-performance software components.

Version 1.0

GA no 952165

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☐	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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Versioning

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
UT	UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS
SISSA	SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE
CINECA	CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO
MPG	MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV
UVSQ	UNIVERSITE DE VERSAILLES SAINT-QUENTIN-EN-YVELINES.
Megware	MEGWARE COMPUTER VERTRIEB UND SERVICE GMBH
TUL	POLITECHNIKA LODZKA
TRUST-IT	TRUST-IT SRL
IPSAS	FYZIKÁLNY ÚSTAV SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED, v.v.i.
IISAS	ÚSTAV INFORMATIKY SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED, v.v.i.
UKON	UNIVERSITY OF KONSTANZ
CoE	Centre of Excellence
NCC	National Competence Centre
MaX	Materials design at the eXascale
Marvel	National Centre of Competence in Research (NCCR) MARVEL is a centre on Computational Design and Discovery of Novel Materials created and founded by the Swiss National Science Foundation.
AiiDA	AiiDA is an open-source Python infrastructure to help with automating, managing, persisting, sharing and reproducing the complex workflows associated with modern computational science (supported by the MaX CoE and Marvel).
QMCKI	High-performance quantum Monte Carlo kernel library, one of the main outcomes of the TREX project
TREXIO	Library that defines a standard format for storing wave function parameters, together with a C-compatible API such that it can be easily used in any programming language
ML	Machine Learning
WP#	Work Package with number
SPC	Single Point of Contact
OOD	Operator-On-Duty
VI-HPS	Virtual Institute – High Productivity Supercomputing (https://www.vi-hps.org/)
CALMIP	Calcul en Midi-Pyrénées
AWS	Amazon Web Services
LUMI	Large Unified Modern Infrastructure

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Executive summary

The primary mission of the TREX Centre of Excellence (CoE) was development, promotion, and maintenance of high-performance software solutions in the field of computational quantum chemistry, physics, materials science, and nanotechnologies to take full advantage of the upcoming exascale architectures.

The TREX CoE targeted primarily QMC methods which are among the most accurate, albeit also numerically most expensive electronic structure methods. In combination with their uninhibited scaling with the numbers of CPUs and GPUs, it is our strong belief that they will become widely adopted in the near future. At this time, though, the QMC community is significantly smaller than both the DFT and the wave function theory (WFT) communities and so is the number of QMC codes available to the community.

One major goal of TREX is to develop massively-parallel quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) codes, highly optimized and made user friendly to run efficiently on future-generation supercomputers. To achieve that goal, a combined approach was used: first, “clean” and optimize target applications and second, develop a library of high-performance kernels (Quantum Monte Carlo Kernels: QMCKL) to be integrated into the codes.

In the previous deliverable D3.1 (Initial report on the performance characteristics on relevant hardware for upcoming supercomputers) covering the first 18 months, we reported the success in optimizing and fine tuning the TurboRVB and CHAMP codes and we analyzed the good scaling properties of the QMC = CHEM code. In D3.2 (Initial public release of high-performance software components) the general guidelines for QMCKL library development were laid down and initial kernel versions (including a simple pedagogic version) were produced and tested.

In the second part of the project (described in this report), QMCKL kernels were optimized and ported successfully across different CPU architectures: ARM NEOVERSE N1/V1, Skylake/IceLake/Sapphire Rapids, ZEN3/ZEN4 and on different compilers: ICC/IFort/ICX/IFX, AOCC, GCC/Gfortran and ARM Clang/Flang. Across all of these CPUs and environments, a single code version was used and obtained good performance and scalability. Then, a GPU version of the library was developed in two “Open” flavors (OpenMP and OpenACC) and ported on three different GPUs: NVIDIA A100, AMD MI210/250 and Ponte Vecchio. Due to the weakness of the software stack on GPU, the porting effort was much larger than moving from X86 to ARM. As a final result on QMCKL, the best GPUs offer limited potential gains (1 to 2x) versus an old full CPU 52 cores Skylake. Part of the limited performance gain is the size of the data used in QMC applications which does not favor full use of the large number of units present in a GPU.

Then, porting CHAMP and TurboRVB codes across a wide range of architectures/software (the same ones used for QMCKL) was successfully carried out. Tuning/optimization effort was pursued, focusing particularly on scaling (intra node and multinode). Finally, integration of QMCKL routines in the three reference codes has been performed delivering from 1,2 X performance gain for QMC=CHEM to over 2X gain for CHAMP and TurboRVB.

Last but not least, all of the codes TREX CoE developed are now publicly available via the TREX web link which also offers support triage.

The challenge over the next decade is to pursue the development of the TREX flagship codes and QMCKL. These developments should not only cover migration to the next generation of computing devices (CPU and GPU) but also the integration of new functionalities in the codes such as new models. This would require the development of a specific software environment (extension of Continuous Integration framework) to support fast code changes. These issues are not limited to QMC codes and they should be tackled on the much broader scale for a vast majority of scientific codes.

1 Introduction

1.1 References for QMCKL, CHAMP, TURBORVB, QMC= CHEM and MAQAO

All of the details (codes and documentation) related to each of the various software used in this document can be found at the websites below:

TREX QMC LIBRARIES

- QMCKL (Quantum Monte Carlo Kernel Library)
 - <https://github.com/TREX-CoE/qmckl>
- QMCKL GPU (Quantum Monte Carlo Kernel Library specialized GPU):
 - https://github.com/TREX-CoE/qmckl_gpu

TREX QMC CODES

- CHAMP (Cornell Holland Ab initio Package):
 - <https://trex-coe.github.io/champ-user-manual/>
- TurboRVB (ab initio QMC simulations of both molecular and bulk electronic systems):
 - https://sissaschool.github.io/turborvb_website
- QMC=CHEM (Quantum Monte Carlo) :
 - <https://qmchem2.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

QMCKL library and the three major TREX flagship codes (CHAMP, TURBORVB, QMC= CHEM) are now all Open Source.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION TOOLSET

- MAQAO (Modular Assembly Quality Analyser and Optimiser):
 - <https://www.maqao.org/>

1.2 Machines

A large number of different systems were used for testing and evaluating TREX code. Below the major contributors to this benchmarking effort are listed.

- MEGWARE benchmarking center: MEGWARE provided access to a large number of different platforms: INTEL SPR with HBM (High Bandwidth Memory), INTEL SPR with DDR5, AMD Zen4 (192 cores), INTEL PVC GPU. All of the systems were easy to use and the support team was very reactive
- AWS provided access to Graviton 3 and Graviton 3E (ARM Neoverse V1)
- AMD provided access to AMD MI210 and W3800
- CINECA provided access to NVIDIA V100/A100 and Intel Skylake
- LUMI (Large Unified Modern Infrastructure) provided access to AMD MI250 and ZEN4
- CALMIP provided access to Ampere Altra Q80-30 (ARM NEOVERSE N1) and Nvidia A100 (TURPAN system)

For all systems, we got a very good support from the system administration team. However sometimes, the real difficulties came from the installation itself. For instance, LUMI supports a 3 layers software: AMD, CRAY and HPE which make issues difficult to locate/isolate. For the GPU development, we also got good support from NVIDIA, AMD and INTEL: due to the complexity of GPU software stack, this support was a real “must”. MEGWARE deserves a special mention for their reactivity, variety of systems and ease of use.

For many machines, we got access to the same hardware but with different software environments, this allowed to test the robustness of our software.

1.3 MAQAO results documentation

All of the performance results presented and discussed in this document are available on a specific Website: <https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/>. On this Website, results are sorted into different directories and will be listed in detail in the next sections.

Most of the performance results presented in this document have been monitored and analyzed by MAQAO. Two types of runs have been used:

Standard runs (unicore or multicore): a single experiment is run and analyzed;

Scalability runs: multiple experiments with the same binary but with varying number of cores are automatically launched and then generate/aggregate a global comparative analysis. This allows to quantify parallelism impact. This measurement technique can be applied for both weak and strong scaling

All of the screenshots were taken from the Global view provided by MAQAO/ONE View. Detailed explanations of the various metrics displayed are given in the table below.

In all of the displays, MAQAO/ONE View uses a simple color coding rule: **green** corresponds to cases where little improvement is expected while **orange** cells refer to cases which could be improved and ultimately **red** cells correspond to cases where major improvement is needed.

Global Metrics

Metric

Total Time (s)

Profiled Time (s)

GFLOPS

Time in analyzed loops (%)

Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)

Time in user code (%)

Compilation Options Score (%)

Array Access Efficiency (%)

Scalability - Gap

Total Time (s) - Time spent by the application in seconds.

Profiled Time (s) - Application profiling duration in seconds.

GFLOPS (optional): Number of Billions of Floating Point (FP) operations per second.

Time in analyzed loops (%) - Percentage of the application time spent in loops (excluding loops present in modules not analyzed by the profiler). It represents XXX seconds.

Time in analyzed innermost loops (%) - Percentage of the application time spent in innermost loops (excluding loops present in modules not analyzed by the profiler). It represents XXX seconds.

Time in user code (%) - Percentage of the application time spent in user code (meaning the time spent in the binary and external libraries specified in custom categories).

Compilation Options Score (%) - Global score based on basic options to use with the compiler to have good performance.

Array Access Efficiency (%) - Processor friendly data layout. Accessing contiguous data is faster. Higher is better.

Scalability Gap (only in Scalability mode): Ratio of Ideal Speedup over measured speedup (greater than 1 and smaller is better)

Figure 1: Global metrics description

Potential Speedups	
Perfect Flow Complexity	Potential Speedup
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	Nb Loops to get 80%
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	Potential Speedup
No Scalar Integer	Nb Loops to get 80%
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup
Fully Vectorised	Nb Loops to get 80%
Only FP Arithmetic	Potential Speedup
OpenMP perfectly balanced	Nb Loops to get 80%

Perfect Flow Complexity - Optimistic speedup available by reducing the number of paths in loops. Having multiple paths in a loop can prevent the compiler from vectorizing the code, decreasing performances. The metric provides an estimation of a global speedup that can be achieved if all loops with more than two paths were fully vectorized. Lower is better.

Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution - Optimistic speedup if OpenMP, MPI and Pthread runtimes are perfect and the load distribution if perfect. Lower is better. This metric presents an estimation of the speed-up at application level if most common parallel bottlenecks are perfect. speedup = MAX (time) / AVG (time without OpenMP, MPI and Pthread).

No Scalar Integer - Potential Speedup - Optimistic speedup if all instructions performing addresses computations and scalar integer computations have been deleted. Lower is better.

No Scalar Integer - Nb Loops to get 80% - Number of loops to optimize to get 80% of the speedup. Lower is better.

FP Vectorised - Potential Speedup - Optimistic speedup if all floating point instructions are vectorized in all analyzed loops. Memory instructions are not considered as vectorized. Lower is better.

FP Vectorised - Nb Loops to get 80% - Number of loops to optimize to get 80% of the speedup. Lower is better.

Fully Vectorised - Potential Speedup - Optimistic speedup if all instructions are vectorized in all analyzed loops. Lower is better.

Fully Vectorised - Nb Loops to get 80% - Number of loops to optimize to get 80% of the speedup. Lower is better.

Only FP Arithmetic - Potential Speedup - Optimistic speedup if only arithmetic floating point instructions are kept. Lower is better.

Only FP Arithmetic - Nb Loops to get 80% - Number of loops to optimize to get 80% of the speedup. Lower is better.

OpenMP Perfectly Balanced (Optional) : Optimistic Speedup if OpenMP loops are perfectly balanced. Lower is better.

Figure 2: Potential speedups description

2 QMCKL CPU Results

2.1 General information

QMCKL contains 3 main routines: AOS, MOS and JASTROW. AOS (resp. MOS, resp. JASTROW) is computing Atomic Orbitals (resp. Molecular Orbitals and JASTROW). These routines produce two different outputs either Value only or Value, Gradient and Laplacian (VGL).

These routines have been tested on various architectures (Skylake, Sapphire Rapids, ZEN4 and Graviton 3) using various compilers (GCC/GFortran, IFort/ICC, ICX/IFX and Clang/Flang): throughout all of these tests on CPU, the same code version was used. In this document, only the most interesting runs (scalability) are presented. A more comprehensive set of results are available and the corresponding links are given in each subsection.

Two data sets have been used: a small one (Alz_small) useful for uncore runs and a larger one (Alz_large) used for parallel and scalability runs.

The main goal of QMCKL is to provide building blocks which first are able to capture a large (ideally at least 50%) fraction of the computations performed by our target QMC applications and second are easy to use/integrate inside applications. Since the standard operating mode of our target applications is weak scaling using MPI, our optimization efforts primarily focused on uncore runs (in particular vectorization).

To improve our library measurements accuracy, a specific mode (called probe) was sometimes used and similarly, a special technique for OpenMP behavior (called prompt) was used.

2.2 AOS Results

AOS contains data reorganization routines (dealing with sparsity) and two loop nests which concentrate most of the computation. These loop nests do not benefit from vectorization because control flow is complex and furthermore a large fraction of computation is done in the “in between loops” which are much harder to optimize. On the other hand, these loop nests are quite well parallelized showing up a modest imbalance (16% max) even on 52 cores (see the metric “OpenMP Perfectly Balanced”). On a 52 cores Skylake, parallel OMP scaling is quite good.

A comprehensive set of results is available at the following links:

QMCKL AOS

Unicore SKL

gcc 300iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_AOS/Alz_small/skl/ov1/QMCKL-AOS_skl-uvsg_gcc_unicore_iter300/

icc 300iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_AOS/Alz_small/skl/ov1/QMCKL-AOS_skl-uvsg_icc_unicore_iter300/

Parallel SKL

gcc 300iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_AOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-AOS_skl-uvsg_gcc_parallel_iter300/

icc 300iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_AOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-AOS_skl-uvsg_icc_parallel_iter300/

icc Scalability Prompt Probe:

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_AOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-AOS_skl-uvsg_icc_scala_prompt_probe/

Parallel Neoverse N1 :

ARM Clang Scalability Probe:

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_AOS/Alz_large/turpan/ov1/QMCKL-AOS_turpan_armclang_scala_f745899_probe/

Global Metrics ?								
Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6	
Total Time (s)	110.51	56.34	29.52	16.30	9.92	7.65	5.99	
Profiled Time (s)	107.64	54.01	27.44	14.32	8.01	5.60	4.03	
Time in analyzed loops (%)	63.8	63.3	62.9	61.5	55.9	51.9	56.6	
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	12.5	12.6	12.7	12.6	11.7	11.4	15.0	
Time in user code (%)	60.9	60.5	59.8	58.1	53.1	48.9	50.7	
Compilation Options Score (%)	60.9	60.5	60.5	60.2	60.1	58.0	52.9	
Array Access Efficiency (%)	82.2	82.3	82.5	82.2	81.7	82.6	84.8	
Scalability - Gap	1.00	1.02	1.07	1.18	1.44	1.80	2.82	
Potential Speedups								
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.01	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.08	1.07	1.03	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.04	1.13	1.19	1.05	
No Scalar Integer	Potential Speedup	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.27	1.24	1.22	1.22
	Nb Loops to get 80%	6	6	6	6	6	6	7
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.11	1.10	1.11	1.10	1.09	1.08	1.07
	Nb Loops to get 80%	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	2.06	2.05	2.03	1.98	1.82	1.71	1.79
	Nb Loops to get 80%	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Only FP Arithmetic	Potential Speedup	1.82	1.81	1.80	1.77	1.65	1.58	1.71
	Nb Loops to get 80%	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
OpenMP perfectly balanced	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.18	1.12	1.16	1.01
	Nb Loops to get 80%	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Figure 3: AOS : Strong Scalability runs on SKL

Compiler: Intel(R) C Intel(R) 64 Compiler Classic for applications running on Intel(R) 64, Version 2021.8.0 Build 20221119_000000

Processor: SKYLAKE 52 cores

▼ Compared Reports

- r0: m1o1
- r1: m1o2
- r2: m1o4
- r3: m1o8
- r4: m1o16
- r5: m1o26
- r6: m1o52

mXoY notation stands for runs using X ranks MPI each with Y OpenMP threads: m1o8 means a single rank MPI using 8 OpenMP threads

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_AOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-AOS_skl-uvsq_icc_scala_prompt_probe/

Speedup (“Scalability Gap”) is quite good up to 26 threads with a small slowdown at 52 threads which is most likely due to memory contention, transfer between sockets and/or a lower frequency due to usage of all available processing units. OpenMP overhead remains limited with a speedup of 1.2x if it was perfectly balanced.

2.3 MOS Results

Most of MOS computation is contained in two simple loop structure which are very well vectorized. Parallelization is quite good (low OpenMP overhead and well-balanced loops). The limited speedup when using the maximum number of cores is due to contention.

A comprehensive set of results is available at the following links:

QMCKL MOS

Unicore SKL

gcc 10iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_MOS/Alz_small/ov1/QMCKL-MOS_skl-uvsg_gcc_unicore_iter10/

icc 10iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_MOS/Alz_small/ov1/QMCKL-MOS_skl-uvsg_icc_unicore_iter10/

Parallel SKL

gcc 10iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_MOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-MOS_skl-uvsg_gcc_parallel_iter10/

icc 10iter : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_MOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-MOS_skl-uvsg_icc_parallel_iter10/

icc Scalability Prompt Probe 15 iter: https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_MOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-MOS_skl-uvsg_icc_scala_prompt_probe_15iter/

Parallel Neoverse N1 :

ARM Clang Scalability Probe:

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_MOS/Alz_large/turpan/ov1/QMCKL-MOS_turpan_armclang_scala_f745899_probe/

Global Metrics ?							
Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6
Total Time (s)	224.87	101.24	58.22	27.40	15.28	11.27	7.27
Profiled Time (s)	213.23	93.15	52.49	23.83	12.30	7.83	4.56
Time in analyzed loops (%)	95.5	93.4	87.3	90.1	89.2	86.6	87.9
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	90.3	87.4	81.8	84.1	83.3	80.9	81.9
Time in user code (%)	95.1	93.0	86.8	89.4	88.5	86.0	86.4
Compilation Options Score (%)	95.1	94.3	94.1	93.1	93.8	92.8	91.6
Array Access Efficiency (%)	99.5	99.5	99.5	99.4	99.4	99.4	99.4
Scalability - Gap	1.00	0.90	1.04	0.97	1.09	1.30	1.68
Potential Speedups							
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.03	1.04
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.02	1.13	1.05	1.06	1.08	1.06
No Scalar Integer	Potential Speedup	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02
	Nb Loops to get 80%	8	8	8	8	9	8
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.39	1.38	1.34	1.36	1.35	1.34
	Nb Loops to get 80%	2	2	2	2	2	2
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.99	1.96	1.84	1.90	1.88	1.83
	Nb Loops to get 80%	5	6	5	6	6	6
Only FP Arithmetic	Potential Speedup	1.10	1.11	1.10	1.11	1.11	1.12
	Nb Loops to get 80%	9	9	9	10	10	10
OpenMP perfectly balanced	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.00	1.12	1.05	1.05	1.06
	Nb Loops to get 80%	1	2	2	2	3	3

Figure 5: MOS : Strong Scalability runs on SKL

Compiler: Intel(R) C Intel(R) 64 Compiler Classic for applications running on Intel(R) 64, Version 2021.8.0 Build 20221119_000000

Processor: SKYLAKE 52 cores

▼ **Compared Reports**

- r0: m1o1
- r1: m1o2
- r2: m1o4
- r3: m1o8
- r4: m1o16
- r5: m1o26
- r6: m1o52

mXoY notation stand for runs using X ranks MPI each with Y OpenMP threads: m1o8 means a single rank MPI using 8 OpenMP threads

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_MOS/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-MOS_skl-uvsg_icc_scala_prompt_probe_15iter/

Speedup (“Scalability Gap”) is quite good all the way up to 52 threads (1.68). The large difference (between 12 and 3 seconds) between Total Time and Profiled Time metric is due to time spent in memory allocation. The two parallelism metrics show very limited potential speedup (less than 1.1x). OpenMP balancing is near to perfect with a maximum speedup of 1.12 x if perfectly balanced.

2.4 JASTROW Results

JASTROW routine is dominated by Matrix Multiply routines which represent over 70% of the execution time in sequential mode: therefore, using high performance matrix multiplies (such as the ones provided in MKL for X86 and ARM PL) is essential for getting high performance JASTROW. Beyond these matrix operations, the remaining computation time is spent in loops which are well vectorized. On a Skylake, scaling up to 8 cores is acceptable but beyond 8 cores the speedup quickly levels off due to manipulation of large data structure. Clearly this routine on a Skylake should not be used with more than 8 cores. Interestingly enough scaling is better on ARM Neoverse N1, offering acceptable speedups up to 32 cores.

QMCKL JASTROW

Unicore SKL

gcc : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_JASTROW/Alz_small/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_skl-uvsg_gcc_unicore/

icc : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_JASTROW/Alz_small/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_skl-uvsg_icc_unicore/

Parallel SKL

gcc : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_JASTROW/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_skl-uvsg_gcc_parallel/

icc : https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_JASTROW/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_skl-uvsg_icc_parallel/

icc Scalability Prompt Probe Value:

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_JASTROW/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_skl-uvsg_icc_scala_prompt_f745899_probe_value/

Parallel Neoverse N1 :

ARM Clang Scalability Probe Value:

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_JASTROW/Alz_large/turpan/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_turpan_armclang_scala_f745899_probe-value/

Global Metrics ?

Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6
Total Time (s)	178.30	95.58	57.82	36.51	25.92	22.82	21.98
Profiled Time (s)	29.45	16.07	9.74	6.32	4.85	4.32	3.84
Time in analyzed loops (%)	24.5	23.2	21.2	17.9	14.7	14.6	14.9
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	23.6	22.3	20.4	17.1	13.9	13.9	14.1
Time in user code (%)	24.5	23.2	21.3	17.9	14.7	14.7	15.0
Compilation Options Score (%)	93.4	93.8	95.0	94.4	95.4	97.5	98.7
Array Access Efficiency (%)	83.3	83.6	85.2	85.4	87.9	88.8	90.0
Scalability - Gap	1.00	1.07	1.30	1.64	2.33	3.33	6.41

Potential Speedups

Perfect Flow Complexity	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.01	1.03	1.05	1.11	1.09	1.06
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.08	1.27	1.58	2.23	2.68	3.16
No Scalar Integer	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Nb Loops to get 80%	4	4	5	5	5	6	5
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.01	1.01
	Nb Loops to get 80%	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.20	1.18	1.16	1.13	1.09	1.09	1.08
	Nb Loops to get 80%	4	5	5	4	5	5	5
Only FP Arithmetic	Potential Speedup	1.17	1.15	1.13	1.10	1.07	1.06	1.06
	Nb Loops to get 80%	1	1	2	1	2	2	2
OpenMP perfectly balanced	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.00	1.06	1.05	1.06	1.05	1.06
	Nb Loops to get 80%	1	2	3	4	4	4	4

Figure 7: JASTROW Value: Strong Scalability runs on SKL

Compiler: Intel(R) C Intel(R) 64 Compiler Classic for applications running on Intel(R) 64, Version 2021.8.0 Build 20221119_000000

Processor: SKYLAKE 52 cores

▼ Compared Reports

- r0: m1o1
- r1: m1o2
- r2: m1o4
- r3: m1o8
- r4: m1o16
- r5: m1o26
- r6: m1o52

mXoY notation stands for runs using X ranks MPI each with Y OpenMP threads: m1o8 means a single rank MPI using 8 OpenMP threads

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/qmckl_JASTROW/Alz_large/skl/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_skl-uvsg_icc_scala_prompt_f745899_probe_value/

Beyond 8 cores, the load is unbalanced between cores. This unbalance does not occur within parallel loops but outside, in the sequential part where a single core is taking care of large data manipulation.

Global Metrics ?

Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6	r7
Total Time (s)	386.74	198.46	103.28	55.98	32.81	21.22	15.58	15.47
Profiled Time (s)	64.36	33.69	18.18	10.50	6.72	4.87	3.98	4.01
Time in analyzed loops (%)	6.57	7.06	8.11	9.73	12.0	15.1	17.8	17.7
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	6.04	6.05	6.48	6.92	7.86	9.37	10.4	10.4
Time in user code (%)	6.59	7.10	8.15	9.74	12.1	15.1	17.8	17.7
Compilation Options Score (%)	43.9	37.0	30.0	22.0	13.9	7.88	4.15	3.29
Array Access Efficiency (%)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Scalability - Gap	1.00	1.03	1.07	1.16	1.36	1.76	2.58	3.20

Potential Speedups

Perfect Flow Complexity	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.03
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.03	1.09	1.22	1.42	1.72	2.06	2.19
No Scalar Integer	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.05	1.06	1.06
	Potential Speedup							
	Nb Loops to get 80%	4	3	2	2	1	1	1
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Nb Loops to get 80%	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.04	1.06	1.07
	Nb Loops to get 80%	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Figure 8: JASTROW value : Strong Scalability runs on ARM Neoverse N1

Compiler: Arm C/C++/Fortran Compiler version 23.10 (build number 32) (based on LLVM 17.0.0)

Processor: ARM NEOVERSE N1 80 cores.

Orange / Red cells indicate that compiler options and Array access efficiency were not available in MAQAO analyses.

▼ Compared Reports

- r0: m1o1
- r1: m1o2
- r2: m1o4
- r3: m1o8
- r4: m1o16
- r5: m1o32
- r6: m1o64
- r7: m1o80

mXoY notation stands for runs using X ranks MPI each with Y OpenMP threads: m1o8 means a single rank MPI using 8 OpenMP threads

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/gmckl_JASTROW/Alz_large/turpan/ov1/QMCKL-JASTROW_turpan_armclang_scala_f745899_probe-value/

Speedup (“Scalability Gap”) is quite good up to 32 threads with an important slowdown at 64 and 80 threads which is most likely due to memory contention and code organization. Parallelism use was good up 32 threads.

3 QMCKL GPU Results

3.1 General information

There are three major players in the GPU world: NVIDIA (historic leader), AMD (a few years later) and INTEL (a newcomer after several failed attempts). Unfortunately, the software landscape is very fragmented: as a market leader NVIDIA is promoting a fully closed world including its own programming language, their own set of proprietary performance tools (Nsight) and last but not least, proprietary numerical libraries (CUBLAS) and AI libraries (Pytorch and TensorFlow) finely tuned to NVIDIA architectures. NVIDIA's strategy seems aimed at binding customers to their proprietary software stack. AMD has taken an opposite approach with offering most of their tool set in open source form but they were forced into proposing alternatives to NVIDIA world which ultimately makes transition difficult between AMD and NVIDIA platforms. The best example of migration difficulties between both AMD and NVIDIA are the BLAS libraries (CuBLAS for NVIDIA and RocBLAS for AMD) which do not follow the reference calling sequence BLAS standard. Apart from libraries, essential programming tools such as debuggers have quality/maturity vastly inferior to their CPU counterparts. To some extent, GPU are not programmable through standard programming languages, in fact they are “usable” through libraries.

The fragmentation of the programming languages for GPUs is clearly illustrated in the table below: many proprietary offerings and very few well adopted common standards.

	NVIDIA	AMD	Intel	Main Issues		
OpenMP	Green	Green	Green			Work
OpenACC	Green	Orange	Red	Really only supported by NVIDIA. AMD claim to have a support but rocm need to be compiled with nvidia lib, and it doesn't really work		Yes but
CUDA	Green	Red	Red	Only supported by NVIDIA		Does not work
HIP	Orange	Green	Red	AMD language, can run on NVIDIA GPU if Rocm compiled with NVIDIA lib		
OpenCL	Orange	Orange	Orange	Lib needs to be installed on the server. Large overhead. Needs to refactor a large part of the code when migrating code from CPU to GPU		

Figure 9: Languages available on GPU

Last but not least was that on the current GPU hardware, data has to be explicitly transferred between CPU memory and GPU memory. This extra overhead appears to be fairly important in practice, limiting the performance advantage of GPU.

For developing QMCKL for GPU, we first decided to remain far away from proprietary solutions (HIP or CUDA). We preferred to favor programming using open standards. Therefore, we chose to develop two versions of the library: the first one using OpenMP because OpenMP was operational on the three platforms and a second one on OpenACC. OpenMP and OpenACC programming relied on directives simplifying a bit the porting and optimizing. While the OpenMP QMCKL was fully operational on the 3 platforms, OpenACC was less successful: it worked fine on NVIDIA platform and with many more difficulties on AMD due to lack of support by AMD. We are finally developing a third version based on SYCL which is Open Source and seems to be more or less supported by the 3 vendors.

It should be also noted that if OpenMP (and to a lesser extent OpenACC) allows to develop codes “portable” across different vendors, getting high performance is another story, this requires either to use proprietary languages (HIP or CUDA) or to use libraries. In our case, we chose to use libraries (CuBLAS and RocBLAS) which proved very efficient for the Jastrow and MOS routines. We also decided to perform as much computation as possible on the GPU to avoid costly transfers between CPU and GPU. This led us to perform some computations in a less efficient way on the GPU

The QMCKL routines were developed assuming that all of the operands (input and output) were allocated on the GPU. Accordingly, we developed a set of ancillary routines to move data back and forth between GPU and CPU. Such a strategy slightly increased development costs but having separated these two functionalities (computation and transfer) allowed advanced optimizations: for example, two consecutive calls to QMCKL could reuse data present on the GPU.

3.2 GPU Performance results

Before diving into performance results, programming environment used on each platform are detailed:

- On NVIDIA, the NVC compiler chain was used. Support for debug was quite limited making code development and source level optimization difficult and painful. On the other hand, once debugging was over, NVC compiler was able to generate quite efficient code.
- On AMD, Clang compiler was used. Debug support was acceptable and code quality seems acceptable too.
- On INTEL, ICC/ICX compilers were used. By far, the development environment offered by INTEL was the most comfortable in particular for debugging. However, for some unexplained reason, combining ICC and ICX in the compilation process was necessary: ICC was required to support MKL while for the remaining part of the code, ICX worked fine. As a result, MKL was not used in our tests. Finally, code quality seemed acceptable too.

In the figure below, detailed timings of the three main routines are given, only timings for OpenMP versions are reported because very often OpenACC was lagging behind. The same routine has been developed in different flavors (using available libraries) to take full advantage of the target hardware. Also, tests have been performed with two different data set sizes using the same methodology as for CPU.

Description of the column headers of Figure 10.

- AO is the standard routine in OpenMP
- JASTROW rocblas for AMD/cuBLAS for NVIDIA is the JASTROW routine using BLAS kernels from AMD (resp. AMD)
- Jastrow device OpenMP is the Jastrow routine written in OpenMP without using libraries
- MO is the standard routine in OpenMP
- MO GPU_BLAS is the MO routine using BLAS kernels.

Compiler	AO (ms)	Jastrow rocblas for AMD/cuBLAS for NVIDIA (ms)	Jastrow device OpenMP (ms)	MO (ms)	MO GPU_BLAS (Cublas for nvidia/ rocblas for AMD) (ms)
Small dataset					
A100 (turpan) NVHPC 23.5/CUDA 11.8					
nvc	2	1 437	3 170	278	10
A100 (Leonardo) 23.1/CUDA 11.8					
nvc	9.6	1 520	3 919	948	47
W6800 rocm 6.0 (AMD)					
Clang	130	3 204	5 584	960	34
MI210 rocm 4.5 (AMD)					
Clang	94	FAILED	6 856	495	FAILED
MI250 rocm5.2 (Lumi)					
Clang	104	1 575	2 264	299	FAILED
Cray compiler	7.2	1454	4 170	501.4	9
Ponte vecchio oneAPI 2024.0.0					
icx	312	NC	2 495	1 447	NC
Large data set					
A100 (turpan) NVHPC 23.5/CUDA 11.8					
nvc	24	4 650	80 170	13 853	322
A100 (Leonardo) 23.1/CUDA 11.8					
nvc	296	4 745	82 365	8 309	1 433
W6800 rocm 6.0 (AMD)					
Clang	829	23 567	120 801	23 541	88 506
MI210 rocm 4.5 (AMD)					
Clang	771	FAILED	143 367	26 063	FAILED
MI250 rocm5.2 (Lumi)					
Clang	399	5 314	50 595	2 409	FAILED
Cray compiler	37	5 239	84 811	24 599	59
Ponte vecchio oneAPI 2024.0.0					
icx	1 807	NC	41 709	11 830	NC

Figure 10: Computation Timings for the 3 main QMCKL routines on NVIDIA/AMD/INTEL

In Figure 10 above, gray colored cells labeled NC refers to Non Compatible options: for example CuBLAS is only available on NVIDIA. The cells labeled Failed correspond to execution failure. These timings do not include data transfer: they correspond to pure computation time on the GPU. In the table above, the same source was used for all machines. On Leonardo NVIDIA A100, we developed a slightly different code version for AO and MO which was much faster (numbers are reported in Figure 13), unfortunately, this version did not work on AMD it is why it is not reported here.

First let us make comments on a vendor basis.

For NVIDIA no failure was observed but for a few cases (MO with BLAS) we observed that Turpan was much faster than Leonardo although both of them used the same NVIDIA card (A100). The issue was traced back to the source code version.

For AMD, we have a few failures essentially on the MO_GPU_Blas version, this seems to be due to Roc BLAS and the issue has been reported to AMD. Interestingly enough, using a different compiler (Cray) allowed us to work around the issue, furthermore CRAY compiler provided significant performance gains. The W6800 is behind which is expected because our tests are mainly in double precision and it only has very few double precision cores. More surprisingly, the MI210 and MI250x (our two AMD HPC cards) have a significant difference in performance, even though they are almost the same card. The 250x are dual GPUs, but we only use one GPU and, in both cases, CPU hosts are AMD.

For INTEL, no failures are reported.

The comparison between the various platforms gives a clear lead to NVIDIA A100.

- For AO, in the small data set case, NVIDIA is a clear winner the performance difference is much larger than for the large data set.
- For JASTROW, for both NVIDIA and AMD, the use of libraries gave a large performance gain. Intel was clearly handicapped on that side and its performance is much lower. Between NVIDIA and AMD, NVIDIA is still a winner but by a small margin.
- For MO, NVIDIA is winning in particular the version using CuBLAS. Both INTEL and AMD are losing because using libraries on MO failed on AMD and was not available on INTEL.

3.3 Some advanced optimizations on NVIDIA

The molecular orbitals (MOs) are computed via a matrix-matrix multiplication between a (dense) matrix of coefficients and the (sparse) matrix of the AOs. Since algorithm running on the CPU were able to take advantage of the AOs' sparsity, we have checked whether the same could be achieved when running on GPUS. We compared the runtime for the MOs calculation on Marconi100 V100 cards by using the Nvidia cuBLAS library v. 11.0 (dense linear algebra optimized for Nvidia GPUs) with the Nvidia cuSPARSE library v. 11.8 storing the AO matrix in the sparse CSR format. In Figure 11 below we report the results for the three datasets h2o-sto3g, Alz_small and Alz_large (defined there via their dimensions).

Figure 11: Impact of sparsity on performance

As it appears from the figure above, and contrary to the CPU case, no clear advantage emerges in using a sparse-matrix algorithm over the cuBLAS DGEMM for the MOs matrix-matrix multiplication for the typical sparsity degree = (#zeros / #elements) found in our benchmarks. This has been further confirmed by tests on square matrices, showing that some advantage emerges only for sparsity degree higher than 90%.

Finally, we measured the overall time for the optimized AO+MO calculation on different architectures, here below a summary of the results obtained on Marconi100, showing as well as a comparison between the openMP-offloaded and openACC-offloaded branches, and between the sparse, dense in single-precision and dense in double-precision matrix-matrix algorithms.

Figure 12: Advanced AO/MO optimization for GPU

The figure 12, also showed that OpenACC did not provide any significant performance advantage over OpenMP on NVIDIA. Also using CuBLAS sparse did not pay off, using dense operations was still faster. Single precision provides a substantial performance gain (close to 2x) but it was only used in MO, AO had to remain in double precision.

3.4 CPU versus GPU comparison

In this section, CPU and GPU performance are compared. For the GPU, only MI250 and A100 numbers are reported. For MI 250, only the numbers for the best software (compiler) are ported while for A100, we departed from our guidelines to use the same source on different architectures and we used a specifically optimized version labeled OpenMP optimized

Small Data Set			
	AO VGL (ms)	MO VGL (ms)	JASTROW Value (ms)
SKL 1 CORE	121,1	849,0	182,8
SKL 52 CORES	6,1	20,7	45,3
ARM NEOVERSE N1 1 CORE	85,1	1 273,6	364,5
ARM NEOVERSE N1 80 CORES	2,4	23,9	42,9
NVIDIA A100 (LEONARDO)			
OpenMP optimised	2,0	4,0	1 520,4
NVIDIA A100 (TURPAN) OpenMP	2,4	10,3	1 437,0
AMD MI250 (LUMI)	7,4	9,0	1 575,3
Large Data Set			
	AO VGL (ms)	MO VGL (ms)	JASTROW Value (ms)
SKL 1 CORE	738,4	8 937,0	3 018,1
SKL 52 CORES	59,2	201,0	447,8
ARM NEOVERSE N1 1 CORE	397,0	13 180,3	6 460,6
ARM NEOVERSE N1 80 CORES	16,6	343,0	405,8
NVIDIA A100 (LEONARDO)			
OpenMP optimised	13,0	61,0	4 650,2
NVIDIA A100 (TURPAN) OpenMP	23,8	322,0	4 650,2
AMD MI250 (LUMI)	37,0	59,0	5 313,7

Figure 13: Timings for the 3 main QMCKL routines comparing 2 CPUs and 2 GPUs.

For AO and MO, comparing a single CPU core with one GPU gives a clear big advantage to GPU: between 40x speedup (small data set) and 30x speedup (large data set). Now when comparing with full CPUs (using all cores), there is no more any big advantage for GPU.

For JASTROW, the situation is reversed, a single core (using MKL) is winning.

Finally, when taking into account data transfer, GPU loses most of it advantages (see Figure 13 below). It should be noted that data transfer measurements suffered from a high variability 5% to 30%.

	Time for the calculation of 1 step (ms):	Transfert	Transfert Back
AMD MI 250 (LUMI)			
AO VGL small :	7,4	141	76
MO VGL small:	9,1	143	73
AO VGL large:	38,5	611	568
MO VGL large:	60,5	611	519
NVIDIA A100 (LEONARDO) OpenMP Optimised			
AO VGL small:	2	35	123
MO VGL small:	3,9	36	123
AO VGL large:	12,5	60	916
MO VGL large:	38,8	55	861
NVIDIA A100 (Turpan) OpenMP			
AO VGL small:	2,4	13	41
MO VGL small:	10,3	57	41
AO VGL large:	23,2	22	314
MO VGL large:	322	104	295

Figure 14: Timings for GPU computation and transfer CPU <-> GPU.

As a final result, there are several factors which a negative impact on GPU use for QMCKL:

1. Data transfer add a substantial penalty to performance. Although some of this time could be masked by overlapping, such optimizations are not easy to put in place
2. Data set sizes used in our QMC applications are not large enough to fully exploit the large number of GPU cores.
3. In a real system, the number of GPU is largely inferior to the number of cores, so the balance between CPU and GPU will be difficult, in particular because TREX code use a throughput mode (multiple MPI ranks). This problem can be worked around by sharing a single GPU between several MPI ranks.
4. Finally, the lack of software maturity in the GPU stack is a strong deterrent for porting and for optimizing

4 CHAMP Results

4.1 General information

CHAMP has been successfully ported and tested on various architectures (Skylake, Sapphire Rapids, ZEN4 and Graviton 3) using different compilers (GCC/GFortran, IFort/ICC, ICX/IFX and Clang/Flang). In this document, only the most interesting runs (scalability) are presented. Across all hardware and software platforms, the same source code was used. In fact, it appeared that most of our optimizations proved to be profitable for all architectures.

4.2 CHAMP without QMCKL

Since the beginning of the TREX project, CHAMP has been carefully analyzed and optimized through a tight collaboration between University of Twente and UVSQ. This collaboration resulted in an overall performance gain of 3X mainly through data and loop reorganization allowing compiler to perform a much better vectorization.

The parallel mode used (weak scaling) provides a very good scaling: degradation less than 2 on 52 cores Skylake while the ideal case would be 1 (no degradation at all).

▶ Compared Reports

Global Metrics ?								
Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6	
Total Time (s)	86.45	88.18	90.41	91.02	93.49	102.13	124.40	
Profiled Time (s)	84.91	85.31	88.19	88.74	91.18	99.69	121.29	
GFLOPS	3.766	7.404	14.442	28.688	55.864	83.141	136.502	
Time in analyzed loops (%)	74.1	75.4	71.7	70.9	71.2	74.6	73.8	
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	71.0	72.4	69.0	67.9	68.3	71.7	71.2	
Time in user code (%)	94.8	93.4	87.9	86.6	86.6	89.8	86.7	
Compilation Options Score (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	
Array Access Efficiency (%)	82.9	82.4	82.1	81.9	82.3	83.5	86.5	
Scalability - Gap	1.00	1.02	1.05	1.05	1.08	1.18	1.44	
Potential Speedups								
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.03	1.05	1.05	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.03	1.08	1.09	1.10	1.11	1.11	
No Scalar Integer	Potential Speedup	1.28	1.30	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.27	1.21
	Nb Loops to get 80%	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.09	1.09	1.08	1.08	1.08	1.09	1.10
	Nb Loops to get 80%	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.98	2.03	1.95	1.93	1.93	1.99	1.89
	Nb Loops to get 80%	6	6	6	6	5	5	5
Only FP Arithmetic	Potential Speedup	1.34	1.36	1.35	1.35	1.34	1.33	1.26
	Nb Loops to get 80%	2	2	2	2	2	2	3

*

Figure 15: CHAMP without QMCKL : Weak Scalability runs

Compiler: Intel(R) C Intel(R) 64 Compiler Classic for applications running on Intel(R) 64, Version 2021.8.0 Build 20221119_000000

Processor: SKYLAKE 52 cores

Code: CHAMP VMC

▼ Compared Reports

- r0: m1o1
- r1: m2o1
- r2: m4o1
- r3: m8o1
- r4: m16o1
- r5: m26o1
- r6: m52o1

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/champ/v2-C60/skx/ifort/champ_mainb31ffd_v2-C60_skx_o1_m1-2-4-8-16-26-52_ov1_ifort_scala_noqmckl/

This is the standalone version without QMCKL optimized kernels but despite that has a really decent weak scaling with a slowdown of 70% at 52mpi ranks. Most of the metrics are good with some gains still possible on better vectorization.

4.3 CHAMP with QMCKL

Using QMCKL within CHAMP allowed a large performance improvement (over 2x) while preserving most of the scaling properties.

▶ Compared Reports								
Global Metrics ?								
Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6	
Total Time (s)	33.23	33.80	34.31	34.97	36.50	39.86	51.40	
Profiled Time (s)	30.59	30.58	31.43	31.90	33.13	36.61	46.69	
GFLOPS	4.428	8.714	17.155	33.692	64.431	95.884	148.722	
Time in analyzed loops (%)	68.2	72.7	65.6	64.9	66.0	76.6	72.2	
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	52.9	56.2	50.9	50.0	51.4	60.7	59.3	
Time in user code (%)	89.1	85.3	73.1	69.7	69.7	80.1	74.4	
Compilation Options Score (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	
Array Access Efficiency (%)	93.7	93.1	93.1	93.0	93.2	93.5	93.9	
Scalability - Gap	1.00	1.02	1.03	1.05	1.10	1.20	1.55	
Potential Speedups								
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.02	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.04	1.05	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.12	1.21	1.24	1.25	1.25	1.20	
No Scalar Integer	Potential Speedup	1.11	1.12	1.11	1.11	1.11	1.12	1.10
	Nb Loops to get 80%	21	21	21	21	21	21	19
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.21	1.23	1.21	1.20	1.21	1.26	1.25
	Nb Loops to get 80%	10	11	10	10	10	9	6
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.77	1.87	1.72	1.71	1.72	1.92	1.79
	Nb Loops to get 80%	29	31	31	30	29	31	26
Only FP Arithmetic	Potential Speedup	1.26	1.28	1.25	1.26	1.25	1.29	1.24
	Nb Loops to get 80%	32	33	33	32	32	33	31

Figure 16: CHAMP with QMCKL : Weak Scalability runs

Compiler: Intel(R) C Intel(R) 64 Compiler Classic for applications running on Intel(R) 64, Version 2021.8.0 Build 20221119_000000

Processor: SKYLAKE 52 cores

▼ Compared Reports

- r0: m1o1
- r1: m2o1
- r2: m4o1
- r3: m8o1
- r4: m16o1
- r5: m26o1
- r6: m52o1

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/champ/v2-C60/skx/fort/champ_mainb31ffd_v2-C60_skx_o1_m1-2-4-8-16-26-52_ov1_iftor_scala_qmckl/

The overall performance behavior is very similar to the previous case (without QMCKL). The main difference besides faster execution time is the impact of vectorization which is much lower.

	CHAMP without QMCKL (time in s)	CHAMP with QMCKL (time in s)	speedup (without / with)
MPI=1	84,91	30,59	2,78
MPI=2	85,31	30,58	2,79
MPI=4	88,19	31,43	2,81
MPI=8	88,74	31,90	2,78
MPI=16	91,18	33,13	2,75
MPI=26	99,69	36,61	2,72
MPI=52	121,29	46,69	2,60

Figure 17: CHAMP comparison with and without QMCKL

4.4 CHAMP multinode scaling

CHAMP was also tested on multinode, both weak and strong scaling. In both cases results were quite satisfactory see detailed numbers in the two Figures below: efficiency remains above 50% for large core counts between 30 000 and 50 000.

Figure 18: CHAMP weak scaling with GENOA based nodes

Figure 19: CHAMP weak scaling with GENOA based nodes

5 TurboRVB Results

5.1 General information

TurboRVB has been successfully ported and tested on various architectures (Skylake, Sapphire Rapids, ZEN4 and Graviton 3) using various compilers (GCC/GFortran, IFort/ICC, ICX/IFX and Clang/Flang). In this document, only the most interesting runs (scalability) are presented. Across all hardware and software platforms, the same source code was used. In fact, it appeared that most of our optimizations proved to be profitable for all architectures.

5.2 TurboRVB without QMCKL

Since the beginning of the TREX project, TurboRVB has been carefully analyzed and optimized through a tight collaboration between SISSA and UVSQ, leading to an overall performance gain of 2X mainly through data and loop reorganization. Due to the complex nature of some loops, vectorization was not very successful limiting the overall performance gain.

The parallel mode used (weak scaling) provides a very good scaling: degradation less than 2 on 192 cores ZEN4 while the ideal case would be 1 (no degradation at all).

Global Metrics ?									
Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6	r7	r8
Total Time (s)	99.45	110.35	118.89	126.72	134.06	141.14	149.00	160.62	184.48
Profiled Time (s)	97.78	108.77	117.33	125.04	131.49	136.88	141.99	147.32	164.75
GFLOPS	2.217	4.004	7.437	13.946	26.353	50.076	94.934	176.151	230.097
Time in analyzed loops (%)	76.2	69.0	63.9	60.2	57.2	54.8	53.0	51.1	49.5
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	28.3	25.6	23.6	22.3	21.2	20.3	19.6	18.9	18.7
Time in user code (%)	81.8	74.3	68.6	64.7	61.5	59.0	57.0	55.0	53.3
Compilation Options Score (%)	94.3	94.5	94.4	94.3	94.3	94.4	94.4	94.3	94.0
Array Access Efficiency (%)	83.9	83.6	83.6	83.7	83.8	83.8	83.7	83.8	84.2
Scalability - Gap	1.00	1.11	1.20	1.27	1.35	1.42	1.50	1.62	1.86

Potential Speedups									
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.10	1.19	1.25	1.31	1.36	1.41	1.45	1.37
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.11	1.20	1.27	1.33	1.39	1.44	1.49	1.53
Potential Speedup	1.30	1.26	1.24	1.22	1.21	1.20	1.19	1.18	1.17
No Scalar Integer									
Nb Loops to get 80%	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Potential Speedup	1.37	1.32	1.29	1.27	1.25	1.24	1.23	1.22	1.21
FP Vectorised									
Nb Loops to get 80%	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Potential Speedup	2.63	2.28	2.08	1.96	1.87	1.80	1.76	1.71	1.67
Fully Vectorised									
Nb Loops to get 80%	22	18	17	17	16	16	16	16	16
Potential Speedup	1.48	1.42	1.37	1.35	1.32	1.31	1.29	1.28	1.27
Only FP Arithmetic									
Nb Loops to get 80%	13	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

Figure 20: TurboRVB without QMCKL : Weak scalability runs

Ideally profile time should remain constant

Compiler: Intel(R) Fortran Intel(R) 64 Compiler Classic for applications running on Intel(R) 64, Version 2021.9.0

Processor: ZEN4 192 cores

▼ Compared Reports

- r0: 1x1
- r1: 2x1
- r2: 4x1
- r3: 8x1
- r4: 16x1
- r5: 32x1
- r6: 64x1
- r7: 128x1
- r8: 192x1

https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/Turborvb/vmc/zen4/ifort/TURBORVB_EO_1a46e7-noqmckl_vmc_cart_zen4_o1_m1-192_ov1_ifort/

Potential gain due to vectorization are quite high. The overall scaling is impressive all the way to 192 cores.

5.3 TurboRVB with QMCKL

Global Metrics ?									
Metric	r0	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6	r7	r8
Total Time (s)	46.56	49.63	51.85	54.19	57.16	60.30	64.69	74.67	96.15
Profiled Time (s)	44.66	47.99	50.20	52.44	54.57	56.01	57.58	61.17	75.94
GFLOPS	1.865	3.507	6.716	12.845	24.329	46.120	86.097	149.211	173.891
Time in analyzed loops (%)	57.1	53.8	51.2	49.4	47.3	46.3	45.1	43.1	42.4
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	35.7	34.0	32.1	31.1	29.5	29.1	28.3	27.0	26.7
Time in user code (%)	63.3	59.0	56.5	54.4	52.0	50.8	49.6	47.4	47.0
Compilation Options Score (%)	66.3	66.5	66.4	66.3	66.3	66.3	66.3	66.3	66.3
Array Access Efficiency (%)	80.8	81.7	81.7	81.5	81.6	81.5	81.6	81.5	81.5
Scalability - Gap	1.00	1.07	1.11	1.16	1.23	1.30	1.39	1.60	2.07
Potential Speedups									
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.06	1.06	1.06	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.02	1.09	1.14	1.18	1.19	1.22	1.26	1.30	1.28
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.02	1.09	1.14	1.19	1.24	1.27	1.30	1.36	1.39
No Scalar Integer	Potential Speedup	1.02	1.02	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01
	Nb Loops to get 80%	9	9	8	10	9	9	9	9
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.02	1.02	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.01
	Nb Loops to get 80%	14	15	14	15	14	15	14	14
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.83	1.76	1.69	1.65	1.61	1.59	1.56	1.52
	Nb Loops to get 80%	33	32	30	31	30	29	29	29
Only FP Arithmetic	Potential Speedup	1.23	1.20	1.19	1.18	1.17	1.17	1.17	1.16
	Nb Loops to get 80%	21	21	20	21	21	21	21	20

Figure 21: TurboRVB with QMCKL: Weak scalability runs

<p>Ideally profile time should remain constant</p> <p>Compiler: Intel(R) Fortran Intel(R) 64 Compiler Classic for applications running on Intel(R) 64, Version 2021.9.0</p> <p>Processor: ZEN4 192 cores</p>	<p>▼ Compared Reports</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • r0: 1x1 • r1: 2x1 • r2: 4x1 • r3: 8x1 • r4: 16x1 • r5: 32x1 • r6: 64x1 • r7: 128x1 • r8: 192x1
<p>https://datafront.exascale-computing.eu/public/Turborvb/vmc/zen4/ifort/TURBORVB_EO_1a46e7-qmckl_vmc_cart_zen4_o1_m1-192_ov1_ifort/</p> <p>Vectorization impact is greatly reduced because a large of the computation time is spent in QMCKL. The overall scaling remains very good.</p>	

	TURBORVB without QMCKL (time in s)	TURBORVB with QMCKL (time in s)	speedup (without / with)
MPI=1	97,78	44,66	2,19
MPI=2	108,77	47,99	2,27
MPI=4	117,33	50,2	2,34
MPI=8	125,04	52,44	2,38
MPI=16	131,49	54,57	2,41
MPI=32	136,88	56,01	2,44
MPI=64	141,99	57,58	2,47
MPI=128	147,32	61,17	2,41
MPI=192	164,75	75,94	2,17

Figure 22: TurboRVB comparison with and without QMCKL

5.4 TurboRVB multinode scaling

Tests on CINECA CPU partition (Sapphire Rapids) leads to some very good weak scaling results (see figure below)

H - 1024 electrons, periodic, no pseudo				
weak scaling				
time (s)	# Cores	# Nodes	Slowdown	Time/per unit of work
865	1	1	1,00	864,91
903	2	1	1,04	451,55
913	4	1	1,06	228,13
1 018	8	1	1,18	127,25
1 348	16	1	1,56	84,23
2 069	32	1	2,39	64,67
2 347	64	2	2,71	36,67
2 360	128	4	2,73	18,44
2 448	256	8	2,83	9,56
2 387	512	16	2,76	4,66
2 407	1024	32	2,78	2,35

Figure 23: TurboRVB multimode scaling

6 QMC=CHEM Results

QMC=CHEM was already well optimized before the start of the project. There the major effort targeted QMCKL use.

CPU	Compiler	Compiler Version/QMCKl	Timing ms	Speedup
Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 (4 cores, 2.8GHz)	ifort/mkl	No Qmckl	24.58	
	ifort/mkl	gcc12 with QMCKL	24.06	1.02x
	ifort/mkl	icx with Qmckl	23.85	1.03x
	gfortran/openblas	No Qmckl	30.58	
ARM Neoverse N1 (80 cores, 3GHz)	gfortran/armpl	No Qmckl	41.24	
	gfortran/armpl	gcc12 with Qmckl	31.91	1.29x
	gfortran/armpl	gcc12 with QMCKL	26.04	1.17x

Figure 24: QMC=CHEM Unicore Benchmark

The benchmark above was run on the C60 molecule (4140 atomic orbitals, 120 molecular orbitals, 240 electrons). The given timings measure the time needed to compute a single Monte Carlo step.

The recent benchmarks of QMC=Chem, particularly with the introduction of calls to the QMCKl library, present a compelling narrative on the evolution and optimization of quantum Monte Carlo simulations for high-performance computing architectures. Historically, the optimization of QMC=Chem was tightly coupled with the Intel architecture, specifically tailored for the Sandy Bridge series through a series of non-standard compiler directives that favored the Intel Compiler (ifort) for achieving superior performance. This optimization yielded significant performance gains, notably more than a twofold increase when compared to compiling with the GNU Fortran compiler (gcc). However, the landscape of high-performance computing is rapidly evolving, with a notable shift towards diversification of hardware architectures and the compilers that support them.

The benchmarks reveal a nuanced picture of performance improvements and the strategic importance of embracing library calls to QMCKl. For instance, on an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 running at 2.8GHz, the transition from exclusive reliance on ifort/mkl to incorporating QMCKl demonstrates marginal yet consistent performance improvements across different compilers, including gcc12 and icx, with speedups of 1.02x and 1.03x, respectively. This indicates that QMCKl effectively mitigates the performance disparity traditionally observed between ifort and other compilers like gfortran when paired with openblas, where a notable performance increase from 30.58 milliseconds to 26.04 milliseconds (a 1.17x speedup) is observed with the introduction of QMCKl.

More strikingly, the benchmarks underscore the pivotal role of QMCKl in democratizing performance across different CPU architectures, particularly ARM CPUs. The ARM Neoverse N1, an 80-core processor running at 3GHz, showcases significant performance gains with QMCKl, reducing the time for a single Monte Carlo step from 41.24 milliseconds to 31.91 milliseconds—a 1.29x speedup. This improvement is not just a testament to the efficiency of QMCKl but also highlights its role in enabling

QMC=Chem to leverage the capabilities of ARM architectures, which are increasingly prominent in the European high-performance computing ecosystem, especially with the European Processor Initiative's endorsement of ARM.

The transition towards QMCKI is more than a technical optimization; it represents a strategic pivot towards ensuring that QMC=Chem remains at the forefront of computational chemistry and quantum simulations, irrespective of the underlying hardware. By abstracting performance optimizations away from compiler and architecture-specific directives and into a library that is agnostic of these factors, QMC=Chem not only improves its performance across a broader range of computing environments but also aligns with the future trajectory of European high-performance computing systems. This alignment is crucial, considering the growing importance of ARM CPUs in the landscape of European HPC systems, driven by the need for energy-efficient and scalable computing solutions. The benchmarks, therefore, not only highlight the improvements brought about by recent developments but also underscore the strategic importance of adopting QMCKI for ensuring the adaptability and sustained performance of QMC=Chem in the evolving landscape of high-performance computing.

7 Conclusions

This document presents the results on optimizing the QMCKL library and three TREX flagship codes (CHAMP, TurboRVB and QMC = CHEM): the results obtained showed high performance improvement (2X to 3X on both CHAMP and TurboRVB) and also very good scaling properties. Furthermore the integration of QMCKL libraries led to extra performance gains: 1,2 X for QMC = CHEM and over 2x for both CHAMP and TurboRVB. The development of a GPU version of QMCKL although very costly due to lack of appropriate software stack provided interesting performance gains but which were offset by cost of migrating data between CPU and GPU.

The challenge over the next decade is to pursue the development of the TREX flagship codes and QMCKL. These developments should not only cover migration to the next generation of computing devices (CPU and GPU) but also the integration of new functionalities in the codes such as new models. This would require the development of a specific software environment (extension of Continuous Integration framework) to support fast code changes. These issues are not limited to QMC codes and they should be tackled on the much broader scale for a vast majority of scientific codes.